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*Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.*

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D6.1 Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

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6	BEN	ALTERNATIVES EUROPEENNES ASSOCIATION	EA	FR
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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package
PC	Project Coordinator
AB	Advisory Board
DEC	Communication, Exploitation & Communication
SM	Social Media

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the overall DEC strategy of the FIERCE project. It defines clear and coherent messages tailored to the various project target groups identified in the strategy, reflecting the diversity of these actors. It includes an overview of communication channels (such as the project website, flyer, social media etc.), presents the project's visual identity, gives a detailed plan for communicating the various project results and addresses the evaluation of the strategy's implementation. In addition, it presents the community of stakeholders to be engaged throughout the project's lifetime and beyond and the preliminary exploitation plan to be followed by the project ensuring the sustainability of the project results.

The aim is to put in place all necessary actions to achieve the desired goals, provide guidelines to partners about the DEC activities through a coherent and structured approach, and to monitor these activities to properly adjust their implementation if necessary.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The DEC strategy presented in this document constitutes a key pillar for the FIERCE project, due to its horizontal role and close interaction with the rest of the WPs. This document serves as a practical guide for project partners on communicating the project to external stakeholders. This strategy will be monitored, updated and reported upon during the course of the project. This monitoring will be based on indicators and the expected impact in the Description of Action and thus it will be a living document that evolves with experiences gained during the project.

Overall, the objectives of the present strategy are:

- To raise awareness and maximise the visibility of FIERCE achievements among the key target groups
- To facilitate the sharing of knowledge within the Consortium
- To serve as a practical tool to implement FIERCE’s DEC exploitation strategy, activities and materials
- To plan and verify the exploitation potential and added value of all exploitable results during and after project’s end
- To build and engage a community of stakeholders
- To establish synergies with relevant clusters, projects and initiatives
- To monitor the relevant DEC activities and adjust, if necessary

1.2 Relation to other WPs and Tasks

The broader goal of WP6 (Dissemination, Communication, Sustainability & Exploitation) is to ensure that the FIERCE results will be leveraged by the identified target groups. The present DEC Plan is directly associated with the outcomes of all WPs in the project since they draw and feed useful content from them. Figure 1 depicts the FIERCE project structure and work plan. The scheme demonstrates the horizontal interaction of WP6 “Dissemination, Communication, Sustainability & Exploitation” with the rest of WPs of the project.

Figure 1 FIERCE Project WPs structure

1.3 Intended audience

This document consists of the plan of dissemination activities that will take place during the project lifespan. As a result, it aims to be a practical tool for the project’s Dissemination Manager and all

project partners to efficiently develop their individual and collective DEC activities and contribute to the project's overall objectives.

In addition, the document can be used as a guide – practical tool for “Horizon Europe” Dissemination Managers of on-going – future projects, who will be willing to explore the FIERCE strategy and capitalize on it, as well as a dissemination guide/control point for the reviewers of the European Commission.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

The document is structured into the following sections:

- The first chapter describes the purpose and scope of the deliverable, its structure and relation to other WPs and tasks.
- The second chapter of the deliverable presents the dissemination and communication strategy of the project, the target audiences, the dissemination and communication tools and channels that are going to be used within the framework of FIERCE’s dissemination strategy and the project’s visual identity.
- The third chapter gives an overview of the community of stakeholders that the project aims to engage throughout its lifetime, as well as the targeted synergies.
- The fourth chapter introduces the exploitation activities including methods, tools, and tactics to explore key exploitable results, sets the conditions for the design of individual and joint exploitation plans at consortium level.
- The fifth chapter of the deliverable refers to the monitoring and evaluation tools that will be used for implementing the project’s DEC strategy.
- Finally, the sixth chapters provides to the reader with an overview of the next steps.

2 Dissemination and Communication Strategy

FIERCE project aims to provide profound theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to understand feminists and opposing actors, activities and discourses and their respective impact on institutions and policies during the period of 2010–2021.

Taking into consideration the project aims and main activities, this section presents in detail the strategy to be followed for the dissemination and communication of the FIERCE project activities and overall results for achieving its intended scope and for making sure that synergies with feminist actors will be achieved and sustained for revitalizing democracy across EU.

In addition, special emphasis is in place to motivate all project partners to be involved in the dissemination and communication efforts of the project, fostering awareness in their national contexts.

According to the **article 17.1 Communication — Dissemination — Promoting the action** of the project’s GA, states: *unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in accordance with Annex 1 and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner.*

In this regard, a “Decalogue” (ten statements) has been developed to help partners properly contribute to the project’s Dissemination and Communication Plan during the whole project duration. The “Decalogue” was firstly communicated via email and then it was presented by the WP6 leader, ViLabs, during one of the biweekly consortium meetings. The document is available in the Appendix.

Considering that this project involves the study of the feminist and opposing actors’ discourses, it is crucial to adopt an impartial approach in order to effectively promote FIERCE results for not

jeopardizing the smooth progress of the project from the potential conflict of interest of the various actors that the project aims to engage throughout its lifetime.

Hence, the present section is structured following the **6W's approach**, a set of questions which outline the project's Dissemination and Communication activities:

- **Why** to disseminate and communicate?
- **What** to disseminate and communicate?
- **When** to disseminate and communicate?
- To **Whom** to disseminate and communicate?
- **How** to disseminate and communicate?

The following sub-chapters elaborate on the enlisted questions to provide a detailed overview of FIERCE's dissemination and communication plan.

2.1 Why to Disseminate and Communicate – Objectives

This part is set to provide context regarding **FIERCE's objectives with regards to the Dissemination and Communication activities**. The rationale for a carefully designed dissemination and communication plan is based on the requirements for attaining the maximum possible impact for the project results by reaching a variety of audiences and communicating the appropriate messages to each audience group accordingly.

The Communication & Dissemination Strategy of FIERCE constitutes one of the main methods to maximise the project's impact and is being realized based on three key pillars:

- (1) Communicate information about the project and the societal challenge it addresses,
- (2) Disseminate information on the project results to the target stakeholders and
- (3) Enhance exploitation and sustainability of the FIERCE's results.

As a result, the project's Dissemination and Communication set the below objectives:

- To identify target groups and identify the appropriate channels to be reached
- To establish core messages of the project and link them with the identified target groups
- To establish and maintain mechanisms for effective and timely dissemination and communication of the project activities and results
- To define the timing of dissemination activities
- To prepare the ground for ensuring sustainability of the projects results after its completion
- To introduce a clear and effective monitoring and evaluation procedure for the actions to be carried out

2.2 To Whom to Disseminate and Communicate – Target Audience

The dissemination and communication plan is based on two levels of strategies for the dissemination of the project's progress and intermediate/final results:

1. The **internal** dissemination and communication strategy includes the instruments and activities that intend to give awareness of the results destined for the consortium members and the Advisory Board and that are not available to the public in general. This kind of dissemination includes:
 - Project meetings and their resulting reports (physical, virtual)
 - Information exchange, e.g., through mailing lists
 - A collaborative workspace document repository
 - Reports, publications, deliverables, etc.

- On-line collaboration through different means, e.g., dissemination report form submission, regular WP and Task-related meetings, online documents collaboration, blog posts and comments from partners, doodle polls, etc
2. **External dissemination and communication strategy** is referred to activities and means which create awareness of the project's partial and overall results. The target of those dissemination activities is specific the project's target stakeholders (see below).

Following the preliminary mapping of the target audience described in the project's GA, the section below further elaborates on the project target audience and what the project offers them to be used also as key messages for their engagement. In particular, there five main groups of target audience:

- **Researchers/Scientific Institutions** will have an interest in the project approach, methodologies, and reports from a scientific viewpoint and will directly exploit the insights gained from research in the project, especially through the FIERCE actions, to be taken up and used in other contexts via publications and scientific articles. Academic partners will take great advantage from FIERCE mainly in terms of: i) increased know-how and scientific knowledge; ii) access to novel framework of movements' analysis, iii) increased visibility in the scientific community and proper accreditation of their outputs; iv) increased expertise, exploitable for academic purpose, v) connectivity and networking with other research and, mostly to civil society stakeholders.
- **Feminist Organisations/Activists** will feed into the knowledge creation process and be key actors in co-designing. They will also exploit the platform of communication FIERCE establishes as they will be provided with the opportunity to participate in a transnational network fostering mutual/peer learning, to suggest, co-create and test innovations in partnership with FIERCE and build their capacity through FIERCE Feminist Summer Schools and all the activities foreseen in other WPs. They will also have the chance to actively participate in dialogue cycles within the FIERCE Labs in order to further develop their agenda, communicate with institutional representation levels and other stakeholders and further expand their network.
- **Policy Makers** with a stake in supporting feminist agendas will be provided with dedicated arenas to bridge with representatives from feminist movements and civil society within the FIERCE's Labs and Transnational networks, so to integrate feminist issues in their political and policy agendas and to enhance their accountability towards feminist civil society. Also, they will get access to hands-on tools and material to mainstream a gender and inclusive approach to their political practices overall and further establish networks and co-creation events in order to uptake bottom-up approaches in policy making and thus create effective and representative policies.
- **Civil Society** will get the opportunity to be engaged in the piloting of FIERCE's democratic innovations in WP4 and will be among the beneficiaries of all communication and dissemination activities undertaken in WP6: those will translate in clear and actionable messages the key project results, keeping them anchored to the 5 thematic areas so that they are grounded in concrete policy areas close to citizen's lives and in order to trigger political action and civic participation. Particular attention will be given to reach out to teachers and educators as movements opposing to feminist groups have often leveraged on concerns of supposed feminist influence on children's sexual orientation and gender identity hindering their straight/ heterosexual identities.
- **Other EU-wide or global networks and initiatives:** In particular, feminist networks shall be interested in utilising project results for promoting their own agendas and activities towards enhancing feminist agenda setting and policy making.

2.3 What to Disseminate and Communicate – Messages

The messages to be disseminated and/or communicated need to entail the project's vision in a pertinent and comprehensive way, highlighting the importance of revitalising alliances between the feminist movement, civil society, and political decision-makers, aiming at a more inclusive and democratic Europe.

The messages of FIERCE should be based on the produced knowledge during the different phases of the project and reflect important moments and achievements through its lifecycle.

To communicate the project effectively, it is necessary to identify concise answers to the following questions:

What does the project address?

We are FIERCE and aim to revitalise the alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers. We envision to rekindle the movement-institution relationship by means of a multidimensional, bottom-up and impact-oriented approach.

We provide an in-depth understanding of feminist and opposing actors, activities and discourses, and their impact on the institutional arena and on policy outcomes, focusing on the period between 2010-2021.

We focus on the systematic construction of eight national case studies including Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain and Turkey and design in addition a comprehensive and cross-cutting comparative analysis based on five policy areas: Labor market, migration, LGBTQI+ rights, Gender-Based Violence & Health and reproductive rights.

Why is it so important?

Increasing social inequalities, political disaffection and the rise of populist and anti-gender radical right groups represent a challenge to our democracy. The EU-funded FIERCE project aims to provide profound theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to understand feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender movements, activities and discourses as well as their impact on institutions and policies during 2010–2021. Moreover, the project introduces bottom-up initiatives that test solutions and innovations in partnership with feminist NGOs/movements/networks to experiment democratic innovation

FIERCE objectives

- *Analysing and de-constructing the gender-binary rhetoric and frames disseminated by movements opposing to feminists, which inherently also fosters homo- and trans-phobic positions.*
- *Identifying discursive and consensus-seeking mechanisms through which the opposing to feminism actors milieus gain traction among “like-minded”, and how these frames are appropriated by the public opinion.*
- *Analysing the complex constellation of alliances that promotes policy positions that are detrimental to gender equality and gender rights.*
- *Investigating the relationship between the contemporary democratic deficit, the spread of radical right populism in different national settings and the proliferation of anti-feminist, anti-gender positions.*
- *Building on participatory research of the feminist movements to explore democratic alternatives and innovations as well as the strength and constraints of the intersectional approach experimented by the feminist movements.*
- *Studying the tensions and conflicts originating from opening up feminism to intersectional approaches and identifying discursive and practical tools to expand intersectional feminist dialogue and alliances.*
- *Utilizing a co-creative and participatory approach to research feminist activities and practices by creating national hubs of feminist movements and political actors from representative democratic institutions, jointly with a transnational EU level network.*

- *Generating knowledge and best practices that can have a transformative impact on democratic approaches and visions.*

2.4 When to Disseminate and Communicate – Planning

The FIERCE consortium has identified three different time phases for its Dissemination and Communication Plan, where different activities have been assigned to different phases of the project: **early in the project, during the project and at the end of the project**, with the aim to constantly review and update this strategy according to the progress and new findings of the project. More specifically:

- **Early in the project (M1-M6)**, dissemination aims to ensure that the project is addressing the needs of its target groups (especially the feminist activists and civil society) and that it is creating awareness and understanding of its activities both within the consortium and among peer groups.
- **During the project (M6-M18)**, is important to inform the research community and policymakers about the first results of the project and ensure appropriate peer review. Moreover, online marketing activities will ensure wide participation of the target audiences in the project's activities (online training programmes, Summer School, community enlargement).
- **At the end of the project (M18-M36)**, dissemination will publicize more generally the project's outputs, the lessons learned, and the benefits gained. The dissemination activities will focus on building up a constituency of support for the project's follow-up activities, as well as on providing evidence to support the exploitation and sustainability of the FIERCE outputs and community.

2.5 How to Disseminate and Communicate – Visual identity & Tools

2.5.1 Visual Identity

The project's visual identity comprises several features and elements that are necessary for the project's promotion and representation, including visual and textual key points. More information is provided at the sections below.

Logo & Brand book

An essential part of building a brand is designing and creating a suitable logo to ensure the recognition of the project and communicate its identity to the stakeholder groups and the public in general.

Deciding the FIERCE logo

At the first stage, 4 potential logos were circulated to the consortium partners via email. Each partner voted for their preferred one and gave useful feedback. Respecting every vote and comment, the fourth logo was adjusted and the final logo was created. The font used was that of the second logo, as partners commented that it was less "institutional" and more "fun", elements that would be more suitable to the feminist movement. A third color was added to the "fist" according to the colors used on logo 1.

Figure 2: THE FIERCE logo “journey”

After the changes that were made, the final logo has been communicated with the Consortium.

Figure 3: FIERCE Logo (Vertical and Horizontal)

FIERCE logo Characteristics

General: Based on the letter “F” and combining it with the shape of a fist, a minimal logic logo was created, easy to use and easily adaptable for any application. The fist shows dynamism, and the “F” refers to the FIERCE project.

Colors: Three vivid colors have been selected for this logo, to avoid a binary approach. More specific, the color code of green (#86bc25), purple (#5c2482) and yellow (#f2b704) shows dynamism and freshness which was the desired effect. The colors used, are gender-neutral and especially the first two are associated with the feminist movement¹.

Typography: The font used is Commissioner, a modern and minimal one.

¹ [Taking A Look At The Colours, Signs And Symbols Used In Feminist Movements | Feminism in India](https://www.feminismindia.org/taking-a-look-at-the-colours-signs-and-symbols-used-in-feminist-movements/)

Brand book: In addition, the project’s brand book was developed providing more details and guidance on the project’s visual identity.

Figure 4: Screenshots from the FIERCE brand book

Apart from the project logo, in any communication material, deliverable, presentation, etc., produced in the frame of the FIERCE project, the flag of the European Union will be illustrated.

As it is stated on the **article 17.2 Visibility — European flag and funding statement**

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Figure 5: EU flag

The EU flag will always be accompanied by the funding acknowledgement statement: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101061748”. In addition, following the guidelines of the Horizon Europe programme, a disclaimer has to be mentioned as well: “Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.”

Document and presentation templates

Clean and functional document and presentation templates are essential to achieve harmony and coherence among the many different documents that project partners create throughout the project’s lifetime. In order to deliver a consistent message to all target audiences and facilitate the recognition of the graphical identity of the project, templates for both text documents and presentations were developed and made available to all consortium partners. The design of the presentation template is aligned with the colors of the logo and the overall aesthetic of the project’s graphical identity, with the purple color being the most dominant.

In detail, these templates include:

1. Deliverable and document template
2. Meeting Minutes template (online – physical)

3. Plain "Letter" text template
4. Template for internal review of documents
5. Participants list template
6. Agenda template
7. Presentation template

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4	BEN	UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID	UCM	ES
5	BEN	SMART VENICE SRL	SV	IT
6	BEN	ALTERNATIVES EUROPEENNES ASSOCIATION	EA	FR
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Figure 6: Deliverable template

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Minutes

Overall

Key points mentioned

WP1 – Anti-gender rhetoric/movements and their influence on democracies
Duration: M1-M26, WP Leader: UL

Task 1.1: Setting up the research framework and mapping actors, debates and policy outcomes (M1-M6)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Task 1.2: Discourses and communication strategies from anti-gender movements (M6-M26)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Task 1.3: Anti gender movements impact on institutional representation and their relations with political parties (M6-M16)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

WP2 – Feminist movements and democracies
Duration: M1-M26, WP Leader: SNS

Task 2.1: Setting up the research framework and mapping actors, debates and policy outcomes (M1-M6)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Task 2.2: Discourses, communication strategies and internal practices and debates within feminist movements (M7-M26)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Task 2.3: Feminist movement relations with other political actors and impact on the institutional arena (M7-M26)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

WP3 – Cross-cutting comparison of thematic areas within a policy framework and feminist contributions to engendering democracy
Duration: M25-M36, WP Leader: AAU

Task 3.1: Setting up the framework for the cross-country comparative analysis (M25-27)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

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Task 3.2: A multidimensional and multi-level cross-country comparative analysis of key thematic areas (M27-M36)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Task 3.4: Cross-country comparative analysis of feminist innovations to rekindle democratic processes (M27-M36)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

WP4 – Participatory research co-creation Labs
Duration: M1-M31, WP Leader: SV

Task 4.1: Research-practice co-creation methodology and FIERCE's Labs set up (M1-M12)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Task 4.2: Coordinating/facilitating co-creation sessions (M9-M26)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Task 4.3: Reporting on results (M10-M31)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Task 4.4: FIERCE actions: Testing democratic innovation actions in partnership with local and national feminist movements (M21-M31)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

WP5 – Innovative strategies and solution pathways
Duration: M10-M34, WP Leader: EA

Task 5.1: Establishment of a "transnational network" bringing together feminist movements and public actors (M22-M34)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Task 5.2: Feminist Activists Summer School (M19-M27)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Task 5.3: Policy briefs and toolkit (M10-M34)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

WP6 – Dissemination, Communication, Sustainability & Exploitation
Duration: M1-M36, WP Leader: VIL

Task 6.1: Communication and Dissemination (M1-M36)

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

© FIERCE Consortium Contract No. GA 101061748 <https://fierce-project.eu/>

Figure 7: Minutes template

FIERCE brochure, poster and banner in English have already been developed, reviewed by all partners, designed and printed. An editable file of the brochure and poster has been shared with all partners to facilitate the translation of its content.

Figure 12: FIERCE brochure

Figure 13: FIERCE Posters

Figure 14: FIERCE Banner

For communication purposes, FIERCE stickers were also developed. They are designed according to the aesthetics of the FIERCE project brand and feature the project logo, the acronym and a QR code leading to the project website.

Figure 15: FIERCE stickers

Based on the FIERCE brand and project characteristics, icons have been developed. They depict the five thematic areas on which the literature review is based on: Labour market; Health & reproductive rights; LGBTQ+ rights; Migration; Gender-based violence. They are used in the project’s presentations, on the project website and social media accounts.

Figure 16: FIERCE icons

Project presentation

An overall project presentation was created in order to present the project’s goals, objectives and the project roadmap in all applicable instances. The FIERCE project presentation includes all the important information that create a clear understanding of the project’s challenges, impact, concept, activities, procedures and expected results.

Slide 1: FIERCE Short description of the FIERCE project

Slide 2: Basic Info

Project starting date: 1 September 2022	Project number: 101061748
Project end date: 31 August 2025	Project name: Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe
Project duration: 36 months	Project acronym: FIERCE
Total funding: 2.490.220,00	Call: HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-01
	Topic: HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-01-03

Slide 3: FIERCE Work Package structure

- WP1: Anti-gender rhetoric/movements and their influence on democracies
- WP2 – Feminist movements and democracies
- WP3 – Cross-cutting comparison of thematic areas within a policy framework and feminist contributions to engendering democracy
- WP4 – Participatory research co-creation Labs
- WP5 – Innovative strategies and solution pathways

Slide 4: FIERCE Impact

- ✓ Effective and concrete ways to ‘engender’ democracy and spaces of democratic participation and governance that can help counteract anti-gender equality rhetoric, frames and strategies.
- ✓ Stronger links between feminist movements and public actors
- ✓ Improved quality of democracy
- ✓ Dialogue stimulation among different positions within feminist movements
- ✓ Contribution to SGD 10 “Reduced inequalities”, SDG 5 “Gender Equality”

Figure 17: FIERCE project presentation

2.5.2 Tools

Website

One of the most essential dissemination and communication tools of FIERCE is the project’s website, whose preliminary version launched on the M2: October 2022, successfully achieving the Milestone 11.

The website’s domain name is fierce-project.eu. All the necessary information regarding the progress of the project as well as project news, materials, etc. are/will be uploaded there.

Figure 18 is a screenshot of the FIERCE website on its current form.

The colors of the website match the overall FIERCE graphical identity, with the purple color being the most dominant on the website's theme. The homepage includes the project logo, the navigation menu of the website, banners with information about the project, a section with the project's latest news, a footer with acknowledgement of EU funding, Disclaimer, contact details, copyright and privacy policy, and links to the FIERCE social media accounts.

Figure 18: An overall look at the FIERCE project website homepage

The FIERCE website consists of six (6) main menus and sub-menu tabs containing information per tab topic. The information is allocated under each tab and sub-tab in order to provide the user/visitor/reader with the best possible experience and guide them in order to find out as much as possible about the FIERCE Project.

Figure 19: FIERCE website menu structure

The website will be maintained throughout the project cycle and will remain active for at least 2 years after the official completion of the FIERCE Project.

All public information on the FIERCE website is available with no restrictions and can be accessed by any visitor with no need to create an account or give any personal data. This information and all webpage-related data are backed on a regular basis.

Website analytics

For the whole duration of the project, and in order to evaluate the performance in terms of reaching stakeholders and acting as a source of information, we use the available Google Analytics as web traffic analysis tool to track the number of visitors and other similar metrics.

A list of the factors to be considered, accompanied by a short explanation, is available below:

- **Users:** An individual person browsing the website (technically, a unique browser cookie)
- **New users:** People that visit the website for the first time in the selected date range
- **Average engagement time:** Provides a top-level view of how long users are spending on the website.

Figure 20: Screenshot from Google Analytics

As seen on Figure 20, for the period 01/10/2022 – 10/02/2023, 874 individual persons browsed the project website. This figure indicates also qualitative metrics, which in most cases are more important than the quantitative ones. More specifically, the average time that a user spent on the FIERCE website is over 2 minutes, which shows that our “visitors” read and engaged with our content.

Website Blogposts

For the website’s blog, the target is to create at least one (1) blogpost per month.

So far, there are already more than 12 blogposts uploaded, in which all partners present the organization they represent, explain their role on the project and express their expectations on project’s results and impact. The second campaign that involves input from the partners has already begun, with partners sharing their thoughts on why FIERCE is important to their country and on the benefits that feminist collectives will gain. These blogposts will be soon uploaded on the website and promoted via project’s and partners’ social media accounts.

All project blogposts can be found on the sub-page [Blogs](#).

Figure 21: Blogposts page on project website

Partners’ contribution to raising awareness via blogposts – news posts

Also, our partners have shared information about the project on their organisations’ webpages as blogposts / news in English or in their native language ([Link 1](#) & [Link 2](#) – University of Ljubljana, [Link 3](#) – The Peace Institute, [Link 4](#) – University of Gdansk, [Link 5](#) – ViLabs, [Link 6](#) - European Alternatives).

On the following figures, there are some screenshots from these posts made by partners.

Figure 22: Website post from European Alternatives

University of Gdańsk | NEWS

academic life science cooperation conferences culture sport open university sea-eu

Home / Academic life / Funding for the FIERCE project under Horizon Europe

FUNDING FOR THE FIERCE PROJECT UNDER HORIZON EUROPE

02.03.2022 ACADEMIC LIFE

Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe (FIERCE) is an international consortium project. It aims to revitalise the relationship between feminism, civil society and politics in the context of growing social inequality, political discontent and the strengthening of the populist radical anti-gender right.

The European Commission has awarded funding to a new Horizon Europe project in which UG is a partner. *“Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe” (FIERCE)*, ranked first on the shortlist, aims to **help understand feminist and anti-feminist movements, actions and discourses and their impact on the institutional arena and political outcomes.**

Dr Grzegorz Piotrowski from the Institute of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, UG

The project is carried out in an international consortium including Vilnius, Aalborg University (Denmark), Scuola Normale Superiore (Italy), Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Spain), Koc University (Turkey), Univerza v Ljubljani (Slovenia), Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis (Greece), Smart Venice (Italy), Alternatives European Association (France), Mirovni inštitut (Slovenia) and the University of Gdańsk.

– *“We want to provide reliable theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to revive alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and policymakers in the context of growing social inequalities, political discontent and the strengthening of the populist radical anti-gender right,”* says **dr Grzegorz Piotrowski from the Institute of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, project leader at UG.** – *“We will conduct the research with the help of frame analysis, political ethnography and social network analysis against the background of key gender debates and controversies in several areas, i.e. labour market, health and reproductive rights, LGBTQ+ rights, migration and gender-based violence.”*

Figure 23: Website post from University of Gdańsk

Univerza v Ljubljani

ŠTUDIJ RAZISKOVANJE UMETNOST GOSPODARSTVO KAKOVOST DOKTORSKA ŠOLA ČLANICE ALUMNI SMUL ENAKOST SPOLOV

INTRANET ENGLISH

Raziskovalne novice

KREPITEV DEMOKRATIČNIH PRAKS V BOJU PROTI POLITIKAH STRAHU

UNILJ > Raziskovalno in razvojno delo > Raziskovalne novice

Konferenca (Raziskovalke in raziskovalci projekta Fierce na prvem sestanku konzorcija v grškem Solunu)

Datum objave: 13.10.2022
 Kategorija: Interdisciplinarne raziskave. Naš prispevek k ciljem trajnostnega razvoja OZN

Cilji trajnostnega razvoja: 5 Enakost spolov, 10 Zmanjšanje neenakosti, 16 Mir, pravičnost in močne institucije (kazalniki)

Oddelek za sociologijo Filozofske fakultete Univerze v Ljubljani je z novim študijskim letom vključen v mednarodni konzorcijski projekt FIERCE (Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe), ki ga v okviru sheme Horizon Evropa financira Evropska komisija. Osnovni namen raziskovalnega projekta je analizirati in ponovno vzpodbuditi produktivni odnos med feminizmom, civilno družbo in nosilci političnih odločitev v kontekstu naraščajoče družbene neenakosti, političnega nezadovoljstva in krepitve populističnih radikalnih gibanj proti politikam enakosti. Rezultati projekta bodo pomembni za krepitev demokratičnih praks in vključujoče družbe ter za identifikacijo in razumevanje problemov, ki v sodobnih družbah omogočajo politike strahu, nestrpnosti in družbeno izključevanja.

V projekt FIERCE se vključujejo 11 partnerjev. Konzorcij koordinira grška raziskovalna institucija Vilabs, pri projektu pa poleg Univerze v Ljubljani sodelujejo še Univerza Aalborg (Danska), Scuola Normale Superiore (Italija), Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Španija), Univerza Koc (Turčija), Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis (Grčija), Smart Venice (Italija), Alternatives European Association (Francija), Mirovni inštitut (Slovenija) in Univerza v Gdanskju (Poljska).

- Raziskovalne novice
- Raziskovalci v objektivu
- ERC in MSCA
- Najodličnejši raziskovalni dosežki
- Interdisciplinarne raziskave
- Naš prispevek k ciljem trajnostnega razvoja OZN
- Vse novice

Figure 24: Website post from University of Ljubljana

Social Media & Channels

Social media platforms are a much-needed part of the FIERCE Dissemination Strategy, as they allow the interested audience to engage with the project and representing its actions via an interactive and direct platform of communication. Through social media, FIERCE can manage a steady flow of information towards diverse audiences during its development and communicate continuously the outcomes of partners' work together with noteworthy information pieces relevant to the Project's scope.

The FIERCE Dissemination Strategy has chosen to utilize social media accounts on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram. Using content that matches the structural affordances of each platform and features SEO characteristics (e.g. relevant hashtags) combined with the partners' already existing accounts, FIERCE accounts are going to be used to increase project's visibility in social networking sites. The use of specific hashtags (#) enables interested parties to be informed about the project's activities and news. Indicatively, the hashtags that are most frequently used for the project's social media posts are:

- #FIERCE, #FIERCEProjectEu, #WeAreFIERCE, #genderequality, #gender, #inclusivity, #inclusive, #HorizonEurope, #EU

Through Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and Instagram information about the project status and activities are made available to the public. The links of the FIERCE social media channels are the following:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/fierceproject>
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/Fierceprojecteu>
- LinkedIn: <https://linkedin.com/company/fierce-projecteu>
- Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/fierceproject_eu/

Regular posts and updates of the social media accounts and a strong presence in these channels are essential for the effective dissemination and communication of the project outcomes.

Also, when videos form the different FIERCE actions and events are available, we are planning to upload them on a FIERCE YouTube account. YouTube links will be shared to other social media platforms, increasing the videos views.

Social media analytics

In order to achieve and over-achieve the project KPIs, FIERCE values the social media analytics. A detailed record of the project's social media insights is being held. These metrics provide a much better view and understanding of the use and effectiveness of the project social media accounts and could be used to verify the actual reach to users and the communities. These insights provide a much better understanding of the social media usage, the actual-real people that have interacted with the provided content, along with their type of reaction. Moreover, via the users' engagement, post likes, post share, mention and such, a much wider audience that it is not being considered via the simple "page like" is being activated and engaged.

Thus, by tracking and considering this information, the project can track properly and efficiently the actual – real involvement of social media users and adjust the project activities as needed. Engaged users interact with brands through interactions such as "likes," comments and social sharing. This "engagement" does indicate the audience health, how responsive these followers are and how many the "real" followers are! The latter is a factor that has to be taken into account when evaluating the strategy, activities and insights of the project's social media accounts.

- **Reach:** The number of people who saw any of the posts at least once. Reach is different from impressions, which may include multiple views of the posts by the same people.
- **Impressions:** The number of times the post was on screen.

Figure 26: Reach of the FIERCE Facebook page for the period 19/01/2023 – 15/02/2023

Based on the analytics seen on Figure 22, for the period 19/01/2023 – 15/02/2023 the FIERCE Facebook page has increased the number of people who saw any of the posts at least once (Reach) by 85.5% compared to the period 22/12/2022 - 18/01/2023.

Twitter

Twitter is a popular and easy-to-use network for sharing short and concise messages. It is a great tool to connect with most of our target groups as many projects and relevant stakeholders use it. Also, project partners have accounts with many followers and dedicated audience, helping in creating more awareness.

Project-related news and relevant articles from other sources relevant to the FIERCE project field of activities are/will be shared for the whole project duration. The Twitter account will be mainly used to promote participatory activities, short announcements about project's news, awareness-raising events, exploitation activities and the project progress in general, as it is ideal for live blogging during events.

A screenshot below presents the Twitter profile with the logo on the profile image and a tailored cover page. Users have access to a short description of the project as well as to the link leading to the project website.

Figure 27: FIERCE Twitter account

Figure 28: FIERCE Twitter account online metrics for the period October 2022 - December 2023

As shown in the Twitter analytics above, in these three months of the project, our Tweets received 7,000 impressions in total, which means that our posts were viewed 7,000 times on this platform.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a professional network and one of the best solutions to build relationships with academics, gender experts, and organisations, and other initiatives.

FIERCE LinkedIn account is mainly used to promote professional content and to promote the project activities, but it is also used to motivate users/individuals to reach the members of the consortium and find representatives of the project in their countries, as almost all the members of the consortium have connected to the public page with their profiles. FIERCE currently has more than 120 LinkedIn connections, already reached the relevant KPI for the first year of the project.

Figure 29: FIERCE LinkedIn account

Figure 30: LinkedIn account “Impressions” for the period 15/11/2022 - 15/02/2023

Figure 30 shows the analytics for the “Impressions” metric for the period 15/11/2022 – 15/02/2023, in which the LinkedIn page scored a quadruple-digit number. For this period, the posts on this platform were viewed 1421 times by different users.

Instagram

Instagram is a powerful social medium that is very popular for multimedia use. As it involves images and videos, this channel will basically promote the pilot actions, making them visible to the relevant stakeholders. Figure 31 depicts the FIERCE Instagram profile as it is seen right now.

Figure 31: FIERCE Instagram account

Figure 32: Instagram page analytics for the period 1/9/2022 – 31/12/2022

As shown in Figure 32, the content on the FIERCE Instagram account appeared 240 times in the first four months of the project implementation. More content will be posted when FIERCE labs and events take place.

Campaigns

FIERCE has already realised its first social media campaign on Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn, presenting the FIERCE consortium. All partners were asked to fill out a template where they briefly presented their organization and stated a few things about their role and their expectations on FIERCE. This text was slightly edited in order to be short, easily readable and direct, according to the social media copyrighting methods and published on all the FIERCE social media channels. Under the hashtag #meettheFIERCEteam, each partner of the consortium was presented, accompanied by their organization logo. The presentation campaign lasted for two and a half months, as every week one of the eleven partners was presented. The presentation text was accompanied by tags (direct links) to partners organisations' social media accounts, so the content was reshared by them and this contributed to the overall awareness increasing and visibility of our online presence. More specifically, the presentation campaign scored quadruple-digit numbers regarding the Reach and Impressions of the posts. In fact, the Twitter posts for the partners' presentation alone were almost seen 5.000 times, as the "Impression" metric reveals.

In the following figures, there are screenshots from the presentation campaign on Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn.

FIERCE
Published by Άννα Παπαδημητροπούλου · November 11, 2022 · 🌐

This week's [#meettheFIERCEteam](#) 🍷 is taking us to Denmark and [Aalborg Universitet](#)

✓ At [#FIERCEProjectEU](#), the [Institut for Politik og Samfund, Aalborg Universitet](#) will facilitate the process of setting up a framework for the cross-country comparative analysis of [#feminist](#) and antifeminist movements across Europe but also feminist innovations through co-creation labs.

➡ The Aalborg University team will help bridging the divide between academic research and democracy in action through cooperation with feminist movements.

Learn more about them:
<https://www.en.aau.dk/>

AALBORG UNIVERSITY

178 People reached	32 Engagements	– Distribution score	Boost post
-----------------------	-------------------	-------------------------	----------------------------

👍 6
1 share

Figure 33: Presentation of Aalborg University on Facebook

FIERCE @Fierceprojecteu · Jan 4
[#meettheFIERCEteam](#) 🍷

[@VeniceSmart](#), an Italian independent research, training and consultancy unit, is leading on the creation of the [#FIERCEProjectEU](#) Labs & will be in charge of the FIERCE Summer School and of an e-learning course.

SMART VENICE^{SRL}

RESEARCH, PROJECTS AND IDEAS
FOR SMART TERRITORIES
AND NETWORKS

[Promote](#)

💬
↻ 1
❤️ 1
📊 200
📤

Figure 34: Presentation of Smart Venice on Twitter

Figure 35: Presentation of Koç University on LinkedIn

The presentation of the FIERCE Consortium is also available on the project website as blogposts on the [Blogs](#) sub-page.

Partners' contribution to raising awareness via social media

On the previous months, the consortium partners have actively contributed to spread the news about FIERCE via their personal and organisation's social media channels.

In the figures below, there are screenshots of some social media posts made by partners' accounts to increase visibility for the project identity and actions in English or in their national language.

Also, partners were often resharing content from the project social media accounts.

Figure 36: Twitter post from Smart Venice for the pre kick-off meeting

Figure 37: Twitter post by partner of The Complutense University of Madrid for the kick-off meeting

Figure 38: Twitter post by the Turkish partners (KU) to raise awareness about FIERCE

Figure 39: LinkedIn post from University of Ljubljana in Slovenian about the kick-off meeting

Figure 40: Facebook post from ViLabs about a Press Release

Figure 41: Facebook post from ViLabs about the kick-off meeting

Press Releases

Within the framework of the FIERCE Dissemination and Communication Plan, appropriate press releases for announcements concerning the news and advances of the project will be developed. Such media material will be published on the project website, on FIERCE's social media platforms and through press contacts of the partner organisations. Translation of the content of the press releases to more languages than English will be conducted where necessary.

The first press release regarding the kick-off of the project has been prepared as a template in English by the WP6 leader, VILABS, and shared with the consortium to be customized by each organisation and be further disseminated.

Also, this version of the press release was adjusted and published in the [Europa Wire website](#). The Europa Wire press release has been included in the Appendix section.

The screenshot shows the EuropaWire website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: HOME, ABOUT, PRESS RELEASE DISTRIBUTION, REPORTS, LEGAL, SOCIAL, VIP, INVESTORS. Below the menu is a hero banner with the text "TARGET.REACH.ENGAGE" and "EuropaWire is the leading press release distribution & newswire service for Europe and the European Union". A prominent red button says "SUBMITPRESSRELEASE >>>".

The main content area features a press release titled "The Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe (FIERCE) project kicks-off!". The post is dated 7 September 2022 and includes a grid of 12 video thumbnails. Below the thumbnails is a logo for FIERCE with the text "The Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe (FIERCE) project kicks-off!".

To the right of the main content is an advertisement for CRITEO with a "Report this ad" button and a link to "Ad choices". Below the ad is a search bar for "24,000+ EUROPEAN PRESS RELEASES" and an "ABOUT EUROPAWIRE" section.

Figure 42: FIERCE press release on the Europa Wire - [Link](#)

E-Newsletter

During FIERCE project's duration, six (6) e-newsletters will be prepared and shared with the subscribed users, which will be circulated approximately every six months. Circulating the project e-newsletter will guarantee target groups are reached not only within the partners' network but also within a larger community of interested potential users. The e-newsletter will include news and upcoming events, publications and strategically report project's achievements.

The project's e-newsletter sign-up form was created via Mailchimp. MailChimp is a privacy enhancing, GDPR-compliant platform, that allows subscription of interested users to the project's mailing list, while respecting all privacy policies that apply in such instances. The e-newsletter sign up form is

promoted via the project social media accounts and partners' contacts. Also, it is featured as a call-to-action button on the footer of the project website to ensure maximum awareness.

Marketing platforms such as MailChimp will be used in order to create engaging and attractive content (a mix of text, images, videos, links, and such others), providing to users with clear, easy to navigate and easy to share sophisticated and friendly content. This is also proven by the engagement data provided by those marketing platforms, an additional feature that provides the project with the opportunity to track the engagement and to adjust the content accordingly in order to maximize the reach and recipients' engagement.

Moreover, via the use of those marketing platforms, recipients have the opportunity to find more about the project, the project's communication accounts, and project activities besides those mentioned as the main part of the newsletter, since they can find all the relevant links and channels, reports and material available in all newsletters via dedicated tabs and buttons, which are part of the main newsletter template for all the campaigns. The content of each newsletter is expected to be communicated to additional (third) users via its' publication on the project's website, via partners actions – sharing the newsletter to their established communities, via synergies sharing, and last but not least via project's social media accounts.

The first FIERCE E-Newsletter was developed and disseminated in February 2023, following the 6-month timeline that was decided for the communication and dissemination of project e-newsletters. It was received by 127 readers, all subscribed to the FIERCE e-newsletter. It is available, as all project e-newsletters, on the project website under the menu tab "Resources" and the corresponding sub-tab "[Newsletters](#)".

Figure 43: Screenshot of the 1st E-Newsletter

Publications

Publications are a significant element for the FIERCE dissemination strategy. They constitute a dissemination tool that informs and engages the FIERCE community about and with the projects' procedures, methodologies and outcomes. The projected body of reports conducted by project partners, is not only going to fuel FIERCE's development but will also facilitate its dissemination planning.

FIERCE publication i.e. deliverable reports and scientific publications will be made available at the project website and uploaded on an open access repository supported by the European Commission, Zenodo. FIERCE has already created its community on Zenodo which can be accessed through the following link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/fierce-project/>.

In addition, FIERCE has created an account at GenPORT, a community sourced e-portal for sharing knowledge on gender issues. Apart from Zenodo and the FIERCE website, publications will be uploaded on GenPORT as well.

Figure 44: FIERCE account on GenPort

Events

An important part of the methods of FIERCE's dissemination and communication is sourced on the real-life, interactive actions that engage target audiences of FIERCE with the project. In conjunction with the above tools and channels, FIERCE is going to be promoted to the community of its stakeholders in ways consisted of the following types of events.

Conferences, workshops, and other events organised by 3rd parties offer a significant opportunity for FIERCE to be disseminated in environments where key stakeholders are gathered. Hence, it is valuable for FIERCE's development and possible impact to participate in events organised by international agencies, fora, and institutions that present expertise around the domain that FIERCE covers. Apart from conferences and workshops, which constitute the main types of events by third parties, project partners can also take part in varying events, like networking events, symposia and/or even webinars.

Based on that, a table has been created on the project repository folders, MS TEAMS platform, to facilitate the information sharing among the consortium partners on events that are relevant to the project and they intend to participate.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
	Title	Type	Date	Location	Abstract deadline	Publisher	Submission Deadline	Participating partner(s)	Short description	Contact Info
1	Queer conference	Conference	28-30 April 2023	Athens	Noe-22					
2	CES	Conference	1 June 2023	Reykjavik	October 17th					
3	ECPG			Toulouse						
4	IPSA	Conference	15-19 July 2023	Buenos Aires	18 Jan 2023				https://wc2023.ipsoa.org/wc/panel/anti-feminism	
5	EUGenDem	Conference	25-26 May 2023	Helsinki	13 Febr 2023				https://blogs.helsinki.fi/eugendem-project/final-project-conference/	
6										

Figure 45: Events database

So far, and even though FIERCE is on the first stage of implementation, our Turkish partners have conducted the webinar “The now and future of women’s movements: Turkey, Iran, and global developments” in which 80 individuals participated. During organizing this webinar, KU contacted various activists and activist scholars and introduced the Fierce project to them. This activity was also disseminated via a dedicated [blogpost](#) on the FIERCE website.

Also, the FIERCE project was represented in the annual meeting of the Assembly of Women’s Shelters and Solidarity Centers, held on 12-14 November 2022 in Diyarbakır. Composed of women's organizations specialized on the issue of domestic violence, the Assembly has been active since 1998, organizing an annual meeting each year in a different city to provide activists and field practitioners a space for sharing experiences and identifying policy demands. One member of KU team participated in the Diyarbakır meeting, contacted with various stakeholders, and introduced them the FIERCE project.

3 Community of Stakeholders

Given the strong co-creative and participatory orientation of the research approach of the FIERCE project there is a dedicated task “Task 6.3: Building and engaging a community of stakeholders” that feeds into the task “Task 6.4: Synergies with related clusters, projects and initiative” aiming at supporting the co-design, validation, awareness creation and help identify barriers and enabling drivers, as well as potential actors that can contribute to maximise FIERCE’s impact.

The setup of an active community of stakeholders will support the project’s activities and their sustainability potential, by actively contributing to enriching the project outcomes, communicating during the course of the project and disseminating results.

Thus, drawing on T1.1 and T2.1 a preliminary list of stakeholders that constitute the projects community to be engaged throughout the project’s lifetime has been created. The list is a living document and it is constantly being updated to meet the project needs. At this stage, there are 171 organisations that have been identified across several EU countries mainly coming from the partners’ countries and Belgium. The full list of organizations can be found in the appendix of this document.

During the next period, the proper engagement of stakeholders will be secured as:

(a) further to the ones mentioned on section 2, tailored messages will be formulated for each stakeholder category also drawing on results of the content and discursive frame analysis developed in WP1 and WP2 ;

(b) a dedicated analysis of the piloted democratic feminist innovations and their benefits for the various stakeholder categories, will be used as a further dissemination and promotion tool and a roadmap for expanding further FIERCE main outcomes.

3.1 Clustering

The establishment of synergies with other related EU-level and national associations, alliances and Think Tanks both on feminist issues and on Democracy in general was envisaged even from the proposal stage of the FIERCE Project. This is why there is a dedicated task, according to which FIERCE

will “seek out collaboration and synergies with other projects, clusters and initiatives in order to plan and implement joint activities, by exploring their complementarity and collaboration potential, thus strengthen the outreach of the project, cross-promotion of results and maximise the mobilisation of stakeholders.”

FIERCE developed a sub-page under the project official website, where users will find information about the Cluster that the FIERCE project aims to create. In addition, FIERCE has listed the projects that study feminism and the role of gender to envision inclusive versions of democracy, as seen on the Funding & Tenders portal.

Projects funded under this topic		
Results: 5	<input type="text" value="Search.."/>	
TITLE ↕	ACRONYM ↑	PROJECT ID ↕
CO-CREATING INCLUSIVE INTERSECTIONAL DEMOCRATIC SPACES ACROSS EUROPE	CCINDLE	101061256
Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe	FIERCE	101061748
ANTI-GENDER BACKLASH & DEMOCRATIC PUSHBACK	PushBackLash	101061687
Fostering Queer Feminist Intersectional Resistances against Transnational Anti-Gender Politics	RESIST	101060749
UNTWIST: Policy recommendations to regain feminist losers as mainstream voters	UNTWIST	101060836

Figure 46: Funding & Tenders Portal: Projects funded under the FIERCE topics

While some of the projects from this list are at their kick-off stage, according to information provided from Cordis, we have already established an initial communication with them, especially with the Coordinator from the CCINDLE project, who attended the FIERCE kick-off meeting and briefly made a presentation about the project.

Also, FIERCE has prepared an online excel file that has been circulated with these projects in order to create a contacts database accessible to all, to facilitate the communication between the different projects and the initiation of clustering activities. The information to be completed by these project can be found below:

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Project Name	Project Summary	Website	Start Date	End Date	Dissemination/Clustering Lead Name	Email	Institution

Figure 47: Contacts database for projects funded under the FIERCE topics

In addition to that, synergies will be explored with relevant projects that the FIERCE project partners have participated. The list with the relevant projects can be found below:

Related projects			
Name	Website	Contact Person and email	Affiliation
ECOPOL	https://ecopol.transoc.es/	Eduardo Romanos: eromanos@ucm.es	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Room to Bloom	https://www.roomtobloom.eu/	Ségolène Pruvot: s.pruvot@euroalter.com	European Alternatives, France
Artsformation	https://artsformation.eu/	Ségolène Pruvot: s.pruvot@euroalter.com	European Alternatives, France
CALIPER	Caliper Project – Caliper Project (caliper-project.eu)	Kyriaki Karydou kyriaki-karydou@vilabs.eu	VIL Coordinator

Figure 48: Active projects related to FIERCE

4 Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

This section presents the Exploitation and Sustainability plan to be followed throughout the project's lifetime to ensure the exploitation of the produced outputs beyond the project's duration both from internal (consortium partners) and external (target audience) stakeholders and therefore ensuring their sustainability. The present Exploitation and Sustainability plan paves the way for FIERCE vision to maximise its expected impact and stimulate the outputs' adoption and effective uptake across Europe and beyond.

4.1 FIERCE Key Exploitable Results

The first stop on the road towards exploitation and sustainability, is the definition of the project's key Exploitable Results (hereafter 'results') that this exploitation and sustainability plan is focused on. The table below includes in detail the preliminary results, their respective goals and the intended target audience.

Key Exploitable Results (KERs)	Short Description	Goal	External Audience	Internal Audience
1. Conceptual Framework of feminism and antifeminism movement analysis	An Interdisciplinary, multidimensional, multi-level framework that aims to build on a bottom-up approach to feminism and democracy.	Develop framework to analyse social movements >8 case studies analysis Develop bottom-up participatory events >Organisation of 24 national level events, 6 Transnational level ones (3 online and n 3 face to face)	Feminist movements and networks, Civil Society Organisations, Research centres/academia, Political institutions and political actors	Academic partners
2. Transnational feminist Network	Establishment of a Transnational feminist Network aimed at a continued exchange of experiences, peer review and scaling up of the experimented democratic innovations at local/national levels	Develop an active community of stakeholders >Involvement of 65 organisations/individuals	Civil Society Organisations Research centres/academia, Political institutions and political actors	All partners
3. Policy Toolkit	Policy toolkit aimed at conveying in a simple and easily usable manner methods and practices that provide	Develop a framework for effective engendered policies	Political Institutions and political actors, Civil Society Organisations, Research centres/academia	N/A

	innovation in democratic engagement			
4. FIERCE's training material	The training material will be the outcome of the feminist summer school and it will strengthen capacities of and communication channels among feminist movements and political actors, foster joint strategic agenda setting, facilitating dialogue between national/local levels and EU democratic institutions	Recorded modules from the Feminist Summer School exploit in other trainings and capacity building >3 trainings organised	Civil Society Organisations, feminist & minorities' movements, Research centres, academia	All partners
5. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt	The overall project experience and lessons learnt by the partners throughout the project's lifetime	Expanding the results beyond the end of the project	Research centres/academia, Civil Society Organisations, Political institutions and actors	All partners
6. FIERCE pilot actions	16 pilot actions will be supported by the project. Their replicability will be assessed to ensure their sustainability beyond the project's lifetime	Expanding the results beyond the end of the project	Feminist movements and networks, Civil Society Organisations, Research centres/academia, Political institutions and political actors	Academic partners

Table 1: Exploitation outputs

4.2 Exploitation and Sustainability goals

Exploitation efforts will aim at contrasting the transnational spread of movements opposing to feminism and sustain transnational alliances of feminist movements. This will imply further developing, replicating and adapting the tested democratic innovations in T4.4 in different countries and contexts, along with T6.4 and T6.5.

4.3 Actions towards exploitation and sustainability

FIERCE defines a credible exploitation and sustainability strategy through an iterative analysis along the project lifetime, including:

1. Co-design of individual exploitation plans and sustainable models to ensure further enhancements of all FIERCE outputs;

The consortium comprises well-established organisations that have the know-how and expertise to ensure the project's results will have the necessary exposure to ensure their utilisation after the project is concluded.

FIERCE consortium is consisted of three types of stakeholders namely **Research centres/academia (AUTH, AAU, KU, SNS, UCM, UG)**, **private sector entities (VIL, SV)** and **Civil Society Organisations (EA, MI)**. Taken into consideration the difference in their scope of operation and needs, a tailored approach will be undertaken to co-design individual exploitation plans to ensure the sustainability of the project results after it's lifetime.

In particular, the aim of the exploitation strategy for the **Research centres/academia (AUTH, AAU, KU, SNS, UCM, UG)** is: i) to promote the wider use of the output of the academic research, teaching and services; hence to contribute to renewed and engendered democratic processes and policies; ii) to enhance academic research standing and the opportunities for its staff and students; iii) to generate additional income to support the academic activities, iv) to provide the space for interinstitutional and multidisciplinary cooperation. Thus, particular focus can be placed on the further exploitation of the KERs: 1,4,5&6.

With regards to the private sector partners (VIL, SV), the main exploitation modality will be the expansion of their network and commercially exploit the project outcomes integrating those into new consulting, training and facilitation services, and to generate new project ideas. This will allow them to increase their customer base and revenues and in addition enlarge their network of relevant stakeholders, creating a larger visibility of their companies and the potential of new collaborations and expansions of their activities. Thus, particular focus can be placed on the further exploitation of the KERs: 2,4,5&6.

Last but not least, for the Civil Society Organisations (EA, MI), the main gain concerns the exploitation of the project's results to improve their existing networks, their capacity, the quality of their work or even to develop new spaces of influence that harness co-creation activities carried out in the project. Thus, particular focus can be placed on the further exploitation of the KERs: 1,2,4,5&6.

Exploitation workshop(s) can take place throughout the project's lifetime to explore further the partners needs and focus.

2. A dedicated analysis on piloted actions and benefits for the various stakeholder categories, to be used as a tool to explore sustainability and exploitation potential;

The FIERCE pilot actions can be considered one of the core activities/outputs of the project. In order to ensure their exploitation and sustainability beyond the project's lifetime a detailed analysis will be undertaken after their end to understand the key specific benefits for the various stakeholders groups and the potential steps to be taken by them in order to ensure their potential replicability.

3. A replication guidebook to support the reproducibility of research

A replication/transferrability guidebook will be developed to support the adaptability to replication and access to finance. For achieving this, a specific number of stakeholders will be selected, and exploration of interests and requirements for exploitation and replication will be conducted.

4. A map of grants and funding opportunities from different donors

Mapping of grants and funding opportunities from different donors (foundations, multilateral agencies) that could support continued work from feminist grassroots organizations will be carried out

and made available for participants to WP4 and WP5 activities and beyond, as part of the replication/transferability guidebook of the project.

5. consultation and verification through the stakeholders' community.

All partners will contribute to this task and FIERCE stakeholder's community will validate the applicability and relevance of the overall work (through webinars and focus groups). These activities will be led by the Exploitation and Innovation Manager (VIL), towards ensuring an effective innovation cycle is in place.

Summary of the roadmap for expanding further FIERCE main outputs;

A/A	Exploitation activity and objective	Audience	When?	KPIs
1	Workshops: Organize exploitation workshop(s) to work with partners on their individual exploitation plans	All consortium partners	Between M15-M32	Define concrete exploitation goals for each partner
2	Analysis: dedicated analysis on piloted actions and benefits for the various stakeholder categories	Pilot partners, external stakeholders	Between M21-M31	Define concrete benefits of the pilot actions
3	A replication guidebook: will be developed to support the adaptability to replication and access to finance.	Feminist organisations	Between M21-M36	Define steps for adaptability and replicability of the FIERCE actions
4	Consultation workshops with key actors to validate FIERCE's exploitation potential	All consortium partners and external stakeholders	Between M21-M36	Explore stakeholders interests
5	Mapping of grants and funding opportunities from different donors (foundations, multilateral agencies) that could support continued work from feminist grassroots organizations	Feminist grassroots organizations	Between M15-M36	Explore grants and funding opportunities

Table 2: Exploitation activities planning

4.4 Management of knowledge and intellectual property rights (IPR)

Project results will be publicly available via a Creative Commons Attribution license. IPRs will be controlled according to the general EC policies about ownership, exploitation rights, confidentiality, commercial utilization of results, availability of the information and deliverables to other EU funded projects and disclaiming rules.

According to EC policies, IPR is based on a) Background knowledge: Consortium partners will bring in their expertise and knowledge for free, retaining full ownership of the IPR of this expertise and knowledge. B) Foreground knowledge: All newly developed expertise, knowledge and technologies will

be owned by the participant(s) that were involved in the development of this specific expertise, and access to it will be granted among project partners for project implementation purposes.

The expected results from the project will be continually assessed in terms of novelty and protection as part of the knowledge management strategy.

5 Monitoring and Evaluation

FIERCE elaborates a specific strategy to monitor and evaluate its dissemination and communication efforts. The goal is to provide concrete evidence about the effectiveness of the DEC Plan, as well as insights on how to amplify its reach and impact. VILABS, as the leader of WP6, is responsible for overseeing the progress of the overall FIERCE dissemination and communication activities. The monitoring and evaluation tools will assess the efforts in both qualitative and quantitative measurements. The procedures to be implemented are the following:

- Dissemination and communication activities reporting by all partners. When an opportunity for a dissemination activity emerges partners should notify WP6 and WP7 leaders (VILABS) about it. The dissemination manager will document such action accordingly and provide any necessary assistance (e.g., guidelines, tips for better communication etc.). What is more, upon the completion of any form of their assigned dissemination activity, partners have to report the activity on the online FIERCE Dissemination Activities Report tool – [EU Survey](#) so that a robust tracking of dissemination and communication efforts is made.
- Statistics of visibility, traffic, reach and engagement rates of FIERCE's website and social media platforms. This will allow partners to better understand the most appropriate timing, communication style and target audience of each message. Furthermore, such metrics are essential for planning re-adjustments.

To produce an accurate monitoring and evaluation procedure, as well as to recognise the impact of the actions carried out, it is essential for all partners to register the activities that they implement on time and correctly. Therefore, all partners should prepare their dissemination and exploitation activities according to their personalised action plan;

All partners should report every dissemination and communication activity they are implementing or contributing to on time by registering them in the online dissemination reporting tool (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/FIERCE-dissemination-report>). As seen at the Funding & Tenders Portal, the types of dissemination activities that FIERCE partners could potentially engage with are:

- Conferences
- Education and training events
- Meetings
- Clustering activities
- Collaboration with EU-funded projects
- Other scientific collaboration
- Other

In terms of communication activities, partners are considered to initiate and report one or more activities shared via the following channels:

- Website
- Social media
- Print material
- Press release
- Media article

- Newsletter
- Interview
- Video
- Event
- Other

5.1 FIERCE Master Sheet

FIERCE Coordinator (ViLabs) has developed a detailed monitoring file regarding every KPI of the project in order to provide an overview of the current project progress. This file is uploaded on the TEAMS project Repository to ensure visibility by everyone working on the FIERCE project. Regarding the communication and dissemination activities, specific sheets have been developed according to the GA KPIs.

Communication Activities																									
Communication channel	Activity	Description	Target KPIs	M3	M6	M12	M15	M18	M24	M30	M36	VIL	AAU	SNS	UCM	SV	EA	UG	AUTH	MI	KU	UL			
				Achievements	Target			Achievements	Target																
	Project Identity and Branding	Create project branding and identify. Finalize Logo and colour scheme.	Y1: Design of templates for project documents, reports and presentations.	YES																					
			Y2/Y3: Update of existing material																						
	Dissemination Materials	Design and production of information brochures, posters and factheets	Y1: 1 brochure in partner languages and English.	YES (eng)																					
			Y1: 1 poster in partner languages and English.	YES (eng)																					
			Y2/Y3: Update of the materials according to the progress of the project focusing on results and generated impact																						
YouTube	Videos	Videos to present project visual presentation and promotion	>3 project videos																						
	Views		>300 views per YouTube video																						
Podcast Platform	Podcasts	Podcasts to share information on the project pilots, the impact generated and the sustainability potential	>8 podcasts (1 x country on pilot actions)																						
	Listeners		>500 actual listeners to each podcast episode																						

Figure 49: Screenshot of the Communication Activities sheet on the FIERCE Master Sheet

Project Dissemination Planning																							
#	Description	Indicative Engagement Actions	KPIs	M12	M15	M18	M24	M30	M36	VIL	AAU	SNS	UCM	SV	EA	UG	AUTH	MI	KU	UL			
D1	Scientific Publications	Feminist Activists online course / Academic articles / Participation in events and conferences	>10 Open Access scientific papers published																				
	Conferences & Workshops		1 Open Access co-edited volume																				
D2	Other Open access publications policy briefs	Feminist Activists online course / Academic articles / Participation in events and conferences	>65 participants involved in the final conference																				
			1 toolkit in 8 languages																				
D3	FIERCE Labs & Democratic innovations pilot actions	Dialogue Circles/Co-creation labs	4 policy briefs in 8 languages																				
			>150 participants in the 3 cycles of Co-creation Labs in 8 countries																				
			> 80 participants to each Transnational Labs online session																				
			65 participants involved in the Transnational Network																				
D4	Synergies/ Clustering	Common workshops/ debate actions	>16 grassroots organizations partnering the innovation actions in 8 countries																				
			> 25 participants to the Feminist Summer School																				
			> 500 users of the online course created disseminate the feminist Summer School																				

Figure 50: Screenshot of the Dissemination Activities sheet on the FIERCE Master Sheet

5.2 Summary of communication and dissemination actions - KPIs

Dissemination will actively support and promote the exploitation and future success of project results, whose uptake and use will be measured during and after the project execution. The plan is based on SMART approach (specific-measurable-achievable-realistic-timely-targeted) with specific and ambitious targets and metrics/KPIs, and a detailed plan.

The following tables summarize all communication and dissemination activities as seen on GA.

As the project is still at the beginning and no results are available so far, dissemination activities of the project results will start after M6.

Dissemination activities	Indicative Engagement Actions	Key Performance Indicator	Available by M6
[D1] Scientific Publications, Conferences & Workshops // Participation in events	Feminist Activists online course / Academic articles / Participation in events and conferences	>10 Open Access scientific papers published 1 Open Access co-edited volume >65 participants involved in the final conference	n/a
[D2] Other Open access publications policy briefs	Policy Briefs/Toolkit	1 toolkit and 4 policy briefs in 8 languages	n/a
[D3] FIERCE Labs & Democratic innovations pilot actions; Feminist Summer School	Dialogue Circles/Co-creation labs	>150 participants in the 3 cycles of Co-creation Labs in 8 countries > 80 participants to each Transnational Labs online session 65 participants involved in the Transnational Network >16 grassroots organizations partnering the innovation actions in 8 countries > 25 participants to the Feminist Summer School > 500 users of the online course created disseminate the feminist Summer School	n/a
[D4] Synergies/ Clustering Common workshops/ debate	Common workshops/ debate actions	15 project synergies	n/a

Table 3: Summary of Dissemination activities and KPIs

Communication Activities	Description	Key Performance Indicator (Year 1/Year 2/Year 3)	Available by M6 (YES/NO)
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[C1] Project Identity and Branding	Create project branding and identity. Finalize Logo and colour scheme.	Y1: Design of templates for project documents, reports and presentations Y2 & Y3: Update of existing material	YES
[C2] Dissemination Materials	Design and production of information brochures, posters and factsheets	Y1: 1 brochure and 1 poster in partner languages and English. Y2 & Y3: Update of the materials according to the progress of the project focusing on results and generated impact	YES (English)
[C3] Project Website	Graphical design of the project website according to the latest UI standards.	Y1: 250, Y2: 500, Y3: 750+ (monthly visits) // 1 blog post per month	~900 visits in total
[C4] Social Media Strategy	Monitoring and updating Social Media Channels of the project (namely Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram)	Y1: 1 post/week (Twitter: 500 followers, Facebook: 300 Likes and LinkedIn: 100 followers) Y2: 2 posts/week (Twitter: 700 followers, Facebook: 500 Likes and LinkedIn: 300 followers) Y3: 2 posts/week (Twitter: 1000 followers, Facebook: 700 Likes and LinkedIn: 500 followers)	Twitter: >115 followers, >36 posts Facebook: >130 likes, >32 posts LinkedIn: 120 followers, >32 posts
[C5] Videos/Podcasts	Videos to present project visual presentation and promotion; podcasts to share information on the project pilots, the impact generated and the sustainability potential	>3 project videos & >300 views per YouTube video >8 podcasts (1 x country on pilot actions) & >500 actual listens to each podcast episode	no
[C6] Networking Events	Participations in conferences, workshops, trade fairs, exhibitions Horizon Europe and other EC events	>30 such activities are foreseen during the project's lifetime.	no
[C7] Generating positive media coverage	Featured articles in magazines and press releases, interviews by European, international, national and local media,	>30 articles >15 interviews >12 press releases >6 E-Newsletters	1 E-Newsletter

	press releases for important news and achievements, e-newsletters for news and upcoming events, publications and report project’s achievements.		
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Table 4: Summary of Communication activities and KPIs

6 Conclusions

This document provides an overview of the project DEC strategy, highlighting its key elements:

- The reason and objectives of communication and dissemination
- The project target groups
- The key communication messages
- The various dissemination channels and tools that will be used
- The planning, monitoring and evaluation of dissemination activities
- The synergies and clustering activities planning
- The sustainability and exploitation initial approach

The dissemination plan presented in this deliverable covers the initial strategy, which will constantly be under evaluation and presents the progress achieved until M6. In addition, updates on the dissemination activities will be included in the relevant upcoming deliverables, D6.2 “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report 1” and D6.3 “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report 2”.

7 Appendices

7.1 FIERCE Communication and Dissemination “Decalogue”

“Decalogue” in Greek stands as “ten statements” that explain and give more information about something.

In our case, this Decalogue is dedicated to proper dissemination and communication activities made by all partners. What makes a partner the MVP of the project dissemination and communication activities?

Let’s find it out!

1. Did you register at FIERCE’s social media pages (Facebook, Twitter, etc.) as a follower?

If yes, congratulations! You’re on your way of becoming the Project Dissemination MVP.

If not, please, take a moment and follow FIERCE on its social media accounts.

[@fierceproject](https://www.facebook.com/fierceproject)

[@Fierceprojecteu](https://twitter.com/Fierceprojecteu)

[Fierceprojecteu](https://www.linkedin.com/company/fierceprojecteu)

[@fierceproject_eu](https://www.instagram.com/fierceproject_eu)

- Monitoring the announcements and posts, “liking” them and commenting on them helps making the most of the visibility of our activities.
- Invite people from your network to the FIERCE online family.
- Initiate the dialogue on social media posts or take part in it.

All these activities are vital to increasing our accounts’ visibility, regarding the algorithmic rules of the social media networks.

Bonus: You can make your own suggestions for posts on [FIERCE’s social media calendar](#) accounts.

2. **EU SURVEY IS YOUR BEST FRIEND** for reporting **ANY** communication or dissemination activity you initiate.

Inform VILABS (briefly) about any promotion activity related to FIERCE (i.e.: Presentation, Publication, Press Release etc.) via email in advance so we can promote it and via the [EU Survey](#) online reporting form after you performed the activity.

3. In the age of visuals, **PHOTOS are kind of important!** Please, collect photos, videos, from all FIERCE activities you’re involved in (i.e. meetings, workshops, seminars, press conferences, etc.) and attach them to the [EU Survey](#).

This material is vital to dissemination activities, such as project newsletters, website blogposts videos, etc.

Reminder: Please, make sure that there are **no third party-intellectual property rights or any GDPR violation**.

4. **Inform VILABS/ALL about relevant EVENTS**, where FIERCE partners could participate (e.g. Conferences, Seminars etc.), so that [events database](#) can be updated respectively.

5. In events organized for FIERCE purposes, it would be a great idea to **INVITE LOCAL POLICY MAKERS & STAKEHOLDERS** in appropriate projects stages and inform them on project’s progress.

Recording of these events (videos - photos) is valuable.

6. Let's be a BIGGER team! Please provide to VILABS [lists of ORGANISATIONS and/or PROJECTS](#) you're aware with whom FIERCE should establish *relations and synergies*.
7. To make it easier for someone to reach our project, please use in all your communications (presentations, newsletters, etc.) the [PROJECT LOGO](#), the [FIERCE WEBSITE ADDRESS](#), and the **FIERCE SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS** (copy them from this document). **ALSO:** Don't forget to use in your communications the **EU FLAG** and the statement "**Funded by the European Union**".
8. **Contribute** to FIERCE Newsletter, Blog, Brochure, etc. with an **ARTICLE** about content, progress, etc. & **distribute** the project's newsletter, brochures, posters, where appropriate.
 - Input will be asked
9. Provide [MATERIAL](#) for regularly updating the FIERCE website (blogposts about partner's progress on FIERCE).
 - Input will be asked
10. **PUBLISH** on various levels (scientific journals, magazines, newspapers etc.). Then, send a copy to VILABS and fill out the [EU Survey](#) form.

Please consider this document as a reminder checklist and not as commands. "Decalogue" aims at helping all partners to contribute to the dissemination of our teamwork throughout the project duration.

Dissemination and Communication, has fun!

7.2 FIERCE Press Release

Title: Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe (FIERCE)

Grant Agreement number: 101061748

Funding scheme: HORIZON-RIA HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

PRESS RELEASE

The FIERCE project kicks-off!

Thessaloniki, 1 September 2022

On the 1st of September 2022, the FIERCE project kicked-off with an online meeting full of enthusiastic partners already eager to collaborate and co-create.

The project's main goal is to provide theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to revitalize alliance among feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers. FIERCE envisions to rekindle the movement-institution relationship by means of a multidimensional, bottom-up and impact-oriented approach. To that aim, the FIERCE project will rely on a systematic construction of eight relevant case studies and a comparative dimension-driven analysis of gender policy issues in five selected areas (labour market, health and reproductive rights, LGBTQ+ rights, migration, gender-based violence). The eight countries that constitute the project's eight case studies (Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain and Turkey) have been selected following criteria of geographical balance, diversity of political, cultural contexts and welfare systems.

It is expected that FIERCE will contribute to a wider understanding of feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender movement activities and discourses, as well as their impact policy outcomes and institutional arena. In addition, the project is going to influence civil society, policy makers, organizations and other stakeholder in order to promote gender equality on a theoretical and practical level through policy recommendations, tools, and solutions.

The project's Consortium consists of 11 partners, among which there are 7 universities, 2 NGOs and 2 SMEs, all with multidisciplinary expertise in intersecting and complementary research areas. Geographically, the partners cover all the main regions of Europe, ensuring that the project outcomes will be adaptable across the Union.

More information on FIERCE will be available at: <https://fierce-project.eu/>

Follow FIERCE on social media platforms for the latest updates on project actions!

 [@fierceproject](https://www.facebook.com/fierceproject)

 [@Fierceprojecteu](https://twitter.com/Fierceprojecteu)

 [Fierce project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/fierce-project)

 [@fierceproject_eu](https://www.instagram.com/fierceproject_eu)

7.3 FIERCE Templates for the initial blogpost campaigns

Title: Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe (FIERCE)

Grant Agreement number: 101061748

<https://fierce-project.eu/>

Why is FIERCE important to your country?

How will feminist organisations/collectives benefit from FIERCE?

Title: Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe (FIERCE)

Grant Agreement number: 101061748

<https://fierce-project.eu/>

TEMPLATE FOR PARTNER'S PRESENTATION

ON THE PROJECT WEBSITE & SOCIAL MEDIA

Guidelines

Title: keep it simple and short – 4-8 words are fine

Introductory paragraph (15-30 words)

Basic information about the organization should be mentioned here (i.e. location, people involved, organization's pursuit, experience etc.)

Main points (~80 words)

Provide details about the organization's relationship to the FIERCE project (i.e. in which WP is involved, expected impact of the work assigned, challenges of the WP assigned etc.)

Final paragraph (15 - 30 words)

A sum up of the above points providing your expectations on

- what your organization will gain from participating in FIERCE project
- what is your overall desire/expectation of what FIERCE can offer in the field of gender equality/democracy.

7.4 FIERCE Community of Stakeholders

A/A	Name of organisation	Type of stakeholder	Country
1	Amnesty International Danmark	NGO	DK/EU
2	KVINFO	Publicly funded institution	DK
3	Sex & Samfund ("Sex & Society")	NGO	DK
4	Dansk Kvindesamfund ("Danish Women's Society")	NGO	DK
5	Everyday Sexism Project Danmark	NGO	DK
6	LGBT+ Danmark	NGO	DK
7	Kvinderådet ("Women's Council")	NGO	DK/EU
8	Søstre mod Vold og Kontrol	NGO	DK
9	Dansk Mandesamfund	NGO	DK
10	Feministisk Forandring	NGO	DK
11	Voldtægtsfres Vilkår	NGO	DK
12	Tænketanken Tora	NGO ('think tank')	DK
13	Cybernauterne	Private company	DK
14	Slutwalk Copenhagen	Activist group	DK
15	Danner	NGO	DK
16	Copenhagen Pride	NGO	DK
17	Dansk Mandesamfund	NGO	DK
18	DareGender	NGO	DK
19	Sabaah	NGO	DK
20	Normstormerne	NGO	DK
21	Verdens Kvinder i Danmark	NGO	DK
22	Center for Magtanalyse	NGO	DK
23	Zonta Danmark	NGO	DK
24	Køn - Gender Museum Denmark	Publicly funded institution	DK
25	Non una di meno	Social Movement	IT
26	Sommovimento NazionAnale	network of collectives	IT

27	Casa delle donne Lucha Y Siesta	Feminist space	IT
28	Se non ora quando	women's movement	IT
29	Coordinamento delle Assemblee delle Donne dei Consultori	coordination of health clinics	IT
30	Obiezione respinta	map of the conscientious objection in Italy	IT
31	Mujeres libres	feminist collective	IT
32	Eskalera Karakola	NGO	ES
33	Feminismos Sol	NGO	ES
34	PPiINA	NGO	ES
35	Colectivo feminista autónomo Las Tejedoras	NGO	ES
36	Forum de Política Feminista	NGO	ES
37	Federación Mujeres Jóvenes	NGO	ES
38	Fundación Mujeres	NGO	ES
39	Partido Feminista	Political party	ES
40	Asamblea Feminista de Madrid	NGO	ES
41	Pan y Rosas Estado Español	Political organization	ES/EU
42	Afroféminas	independent media	ES
43	Feministas por el Clima	NGO	ES
44	Calala	Foundation	ES
45	Pikara Magazine	Communication and Journalism Cooperative	ES
46	ATH-ELE Asociación de Trabajadoras de Hogar (Bilbao)	NGO	ES
47	Rosa Luxemburg Madrid	Foundation	ES (International, founded in Germany)
48	Centrum Praw Kobiet	foundation	PL
49	Fundacja Feminoteka/Feminoteka Foundation	foundation	PL
50	Fundacja na rzecz Kobiet i Planowania Rodziny (FEDERA)/The Foundation for Women and Family Planning	foundation	PL

51	Ogólnopolski Strak Kobiet (OSK)/The All-Poland Women's Strike (OSK)	foundation, previously a social movement	PL
52	Dziewuchy Dziewuchom/Gals for Gals	foundation, previously a social movement	PL
53	Aborcja Bez Granic/ Abortion Without Borders	network	PL
54	Porozumienie Kobiet 8 Marca/Women's Agreement of 8 March	informal group	PL
55	Stowarzyszenie Kongres Kobiet/The Congress of Women Association	association	PL
56	Ośrodek Informacji Środowisk Kobietych OŚKA/The National Women's Information Centre OŚKA	NGO	PL
57	Ogólnopolskie Pogotowie Dla Ofiar Przemocy w Rodzinie „Niebieska Linia”/ The Polish Nationwide Emergency Service for Victims of Domestic Violence	NGO	PL
58	Fundacja „Pomoc Kobietom i Dzieciom”/ The "Help for Women and Children" Foundation	foundation	PL
59	Bodrum Kadın Dayanışma Derneği	feminist NGO	TR/EU
60	İzmir Kadın Dayanışma Derneği	feminist NGO	TR/EU
61	Kadın Zamanı Derneği	feminist NGO	TR/EU
62	Uluslararası Göçmen Kadınlar Dayanışma Derneği	feminist NGO	TR
63	Kaos-GL	professional LGBTQ organization	TR/EU
64	Lambda Istanbul	professional LGBTQ organization	TR/EU
65	Cinsel Sağlık ve Üreme Sağlığı Hakları Platformu	feminist NGO	TR/EU
66	Kadın Cinayetlerini Durduracağız Platformu	NGO	TR/EU
67	ŠKUC Lesbian Lilith (LL) and Magnus	Established by ŠKUC (NGO)	SI
68	Amnesty International Slovenia	NGO	SI
69	SOS telephone line for women and children	NGO	SI
70	Association for Nonviolent Communication	NGO	SI

71	City of women	NGO	SI
72	Cultural Informational and Counselling Centre Legebitra	NGO	SI
73	Feminist and Queer Festival Red Dawns	autonomous feminist queer festival	SI
74	Women's Lobby Slovenia	NGO	SI
75	Equal opportunities coordinator at Municipality of Ljubljana	advisory body	SI
76	Kombinat	autonomous group	SI
77	Lesbian Feminist University (LFU)	autonomous group	SI
78	Iskra Working Committee on Feminism (DoFEM)	Established by Iskra (NGO)	SI
79	Equal Opportunities Division at Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities	unit/interme diate level within the Ministry	SI
80	Feminist Action (FemA)	autonomous group	SI
81	TransAkcija	NGO	SI
82	Z'borke	autonomous group	SI
83	Spol.si	Portal spol.si is published by the Association for Promoting Equality and Pluralism Vita Activa	SI
84	Advocate of the Principle of Equality	autonomous state body	SI
85	The 8th March Institute	NGO	SI
86	Gender Equality Expert Council	advisory body	SI
87	Rezistenca	research group (autonomou s)	SI
88	She Knows Association	NGO	SI

89	European Women's Lobby (EWL)	NGO	BE
90	WIDE+	NGO	BE
91	European Women Alliance (EWA)	NGO	BE
92	WAVE - Women Against Violence Europe	Network of associations	AT
93	E.A.S.T. (Essential Autonomous Struggles Transnational)	Movement/collective	
94	Friedrich Ebert Stiftung (FES)	NGO/Foundation	Bosnia and Herzegovina
95	Gender 5+	Think tank	BE
96	The Alliance of Her - ALDE	Federation of parties	BE
97	Women's Committee of the European Trade Union Confederation (ETUC)	Trade union	BE
98	European Young Women's Christian Association (European YWCA)	NGO	SE
99	Centre for Intersectional Justice	NGO	DE
100	Heinrich Böll Stiftung	Think tank & foundation	DE
101	European Parliamentary Forum for Sexual & Reproductive Rights	Network of individuals	BE
102	Gunda Werner Institute (GWI)	Think tank	DE
103	Green European Foundation	Foundation	LU
104	European Institute of Women's Health (EIWH)	NGO	IR
105	European Women Lawyers Association	NGO	BE
106	European Sex Workers Rights Alliance (ESWA) (prev. ICRSE)	NGO	NL
107	International Lesbian and Gay Organisation - ILGA Europe	NGO	BE
108	The Greens/European Free Alliance	Federation of parties	BE
109	The Left (GUE/NGL)	Federation of parties	BE
110	Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats (S&D)	Federation of parties	LU
111	MeTooEP	Movement/collective	BE
112	European Network of Migrant Women (ENoW)	NGO	BE
113	Karat (Coalition for Gender Equality)	NGO	PL
114	Women Engage for a Common Future (WECF)	NGO	NL
115	Young Feminist Europe (YFE)	NGO	BE
116	Open Society Foundations	Foundation	USA

117	AtGender	Association	NL
118	Fuerza femenina	Autonomous group	EL
119	Κιουρί@	Autonomous group	EL
120	KamiaAnohi	Autonomous group	EL
121	Φεμινιστική Ομάδα Κιλοτίνα	Autonomous group	EL
122	Συνέλευση 8ης Μάρτη	Autonomous group	EL
123	Sabbat - Burn the Rich not the Witch	Autonomous group	EL
124	Bra stards	Autonomous group	EL
125	JUSTICE 4 ZAK/ZACKIE	Autonomous group	EL
126	Χωρίς Συναίνεση Είναι Βιασμός	Autonomous group	EL
127	Feminist Solidarity Initiative with Konstantina Kouneva	Autonomous group	EL
128	Colour Youth	NGO	EL
129	G-All	NGO	EL
130	Genderhood	NGO	EL
131	Orlando LGBTQ+	NGO	EL
132	Proud Seniors	NGO	EL
133	To mov	SCE	EL
134	Rainbow School	NGO	EL
135	rainbow families greece	NGO	EL
136	Ομοφυλοφιλική & Λεσβιακή Κοινότητα Ελλάδας Ομοφυλοφιλική Λεσβιακή Κοινότητα Ελλάδας	NGO	EL
137	Thessaloniki Pride	NGO	EL
138	United African Women Organization	N/A	EL
139	Feminist Autonomous Centre for research	NGO	EL
140	KETHI	Institutional	EL
141	General Secretariat for Demography and Family Policy and Gender Equality	Institutional	EL
142	Diotima	NGO	EL
143	Ombudsperson (Sector of equal treatment)	Institutional	EL

144	Gender equality committee of Central Union of Municipalities of Greece (KEDE)	Institutional	EL
145	Gender equality office of Central Union of Municipalities of Greece (KEDE)	Institutional	EL
146	Gender Equality office of the Association of Greek Regions (EN.P.E.)	Institutional	EL
147	Enosi Ginaikon Ellados	political party organisation	EL
148	Federetion of women of Greece	political party organisation	EL
149	Kinisi Dhokratikon Ginaikon	political party organisation	EL
150	Center for Gender Studies – Panteion University	university	EL
151	Phylis – AUTH	NGO	EL
152	Culture Border Gender Laboratory – University of Macedonia Culture	Institutional	EL
153	Nous Toutes	Movement / Organisation	FR
154	Lallab	Movement / Organisation	FR/EU
155	Feminists contre le cyberharcèlement	Movement / Organisation	FR
156	STRASS	Trade Union	FR/EU
157	Planning Familial (PF)	Movement / Organisation	FR
158	Observatory of Sexual Violence in Politics	Observatory	FR
159	Femen	movement / Organisation	FR
160	La Barbe	collective	FR
161	Osez le féminisme	Movement / Organisation	FR
162	Mwasi	Movement / Organisation	FR
163	Inter-organisation Féminicides	coalition	FR
164	Mor-Çatı Kadın Sığınağı Vakfı	feminist NGO	TR/EU
165	Kadının İnsan Hakları Yeni Çözümler	feminist NGO	TR/EU

166	Kadınlara Dayanışma Vakfı	feminist NGO	TR/EU
167	Ankara Kadın Dayanışma Vakfı	feminist NGO	TR
168	Uçan Süpürge	feminist NGO	TR/EU
169	KAMER	feminist NGO	TR/EU
170	Cinsel Şiddetle Mücadele Derneği	feminist NGO	TR/EU
171	Rosa Kadın Derneği	feminist NGO	TR/EU